

NUMERICAL STUDY OF ACTIVE FLOW SEPARATION CONTROL FOR UHBR ENGINE INTEGRATION ON GENERIC WING IN HIGH-LIFT CONFIGURATION

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ABSTRACT:

The close coupling of the ultra-high bypass ratio (UHBR) engine on a modern airliner poses a challenging task. The large engine nacelle diameter and a close coupling to the wing require slat cut-outs. In the attempt to remedy for the maximum lift loss, the Active Flow Control (AFC) is employed. The effect of steady suction and oscillatory blowing on local flow separation in the slat cut-out region downstream of a UHBR engine pylon is investigated by CFD URANS simulations. The simulation environment reflects the wind tunnel test conducted at the low speed wind tunnel at Tel-Aviv University. The validated CFD results are employed to assess the effects individual actuation mechanisms (steady suction, oscillatory blowing and a combination of both). Both investigated flow control mechanisms are effective in significant reduction of the flow separation. The AFC applied close to the leading edge in the slat cut-out region affects the flow field on large parts of the upper wing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ultra-High Bypass ratio (UHBR) engines represent one opportunity to move towards the goal of reducing environmental footprint of aviation industry, which is will be growing according to the available forecasts [1]. However, the large nacelle diameter of such engines presents significant integration challenges, as the close wing-nacelle coupling requires a large slat cut-out to avoid structural collisions during take-off and landing. The missing slat leads to premature flow separation on the wing and thus to degradation of maximum lift. While part of the inevitable flow separation can be postponed toward higher incidence angle by passive means, such as nacelle strakes [2], their effect is limited. Active

Flow Control (AFC) has already demonstrated its potential to postpone flow separation, but most of the AFC devices require large amounts of energy or mass flow [14]. There-fore, within the EU funded CleanSky2 project INAFLOWT [3], the goal is to combine steady suction with oscillatory blowing to reduce actuation energy requirements. The small scale wind tunnel testing is aimed to establish optimal AFC actuation location and parameters. The results will be applied to the scale wind tunnel tests of a representative UHBR high-lift configuration to evaluate efficiency in the representative scale.

The AFC device proposed to fulfil this task is the Suction and Oscillatory Blowing (SaOB) actuator, which significantly reduces mass flow requirements and safety issues [9], mainly due to the fact that the actuator provides steady suction as a by-product of its operation and, furthermore, it does not require any moving parts to establish flow oscillations.

The present paper discusses numerical simulations of preliminary tests using a downscaled UHBR high-lift configuration, their promising results, and validation by wind tunnel experiments.

Extensive study of the wind tunnel wall and Reynolds number effects has been done ahead [5]. Based on these results, a series of CFD simulations has been performed to identify a suitable AFC setup (chord-wise position, span-wise distribution, actuation magnitude) for the small scale wind tunnel experiment ($Re=1.3$ million) [7]. It was shown by CFD simulations that even steady suction alone, applied close to leading edge, can significantly reduce flow separation region, postpone it to higher angles of attack (AoA), and provide corresponding benefit in lift in the order of 3-4 lift counts ($1lc=0.01 \delta C_L$). Combined with oscillatory blowing, the benefit of actuation is even higher (up to the order of 6 lift counts). Physically relevant actuation parameters (blowing velocity and oscillation frequency) were considered based on known properties of the proposed AFC actuator [9]. The CFD results were validated by existing wind tunnel data [7].

The ability to mitigate the loss of lift due to UHBR engine integration is a crucial task for safe and reliable operation. The promising results documented in the present work demonstrate the benefit of advanced AFC actuation, especially in terms of mass flow requirements when compared to state-of-the-art technologies. The aim is to pave a way for the large scale wind tunnel testing ($Re=11$ million) with integrated advanced AFC. The paper is organized as follows In Section 2 the experimental setup and the background behind the project goals is briefly explained. Furthermore, the SaOB actuator which will be used for AFC actuation is presented and its operation is briefly explained. In Section 3 the CFD setup and its relation to the wind tunnel experiment is described. In Section 4 the results are discussed and the Conclusion is given in Section 5.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND REFERENCE CASE DESCRIPTION

The experiments were performed in the Knapp-Meadow low-speed wind tunnel at Tel-Aviv University. It is an atmospheric wind tunnel with a closed test section of dimensions 0.61m x 1.5m x 4.25m (width x height x test section length). The wind tunnel model used within this study was derived by scaling down the large-scale wind tunnel model (LSM) used during the AFloNext project [4], see Figure 1, with a scaling factor of 1:8.4. The wing represents a 2.5D high-lift wing configuration based on DLR-F15 airfoil with a sweep angle of 28° and an extended slat cut-out in the pylon wake region for integration of the UHBR engine nacelle. This small scale model (SSM) represents a landing configuration with deployed flap and a slat.

Figure 1: Large scale model with side plates, which will be tested in the TsAGI wind tunnel.

The UHBR engine is represented by two part (inner core, outer nacelle) underwing-mounted flow-through nacelle. An enlarged strake is mounted to the inboard side of the nacelle. The wing has a reference chord length of about 0.39m (nominal chord of an airfoil perpendicular to the leading edge, with retracted high-lift devices) and a spanwise extension of 0.61m, corresponding to the

wall-to-wall horizontal mounting in the wind tunnel section. A leading edge extension (LEX) was added to the outboard corner slat during the design of the large scale model to postpone the separation in the corner between the outboard wing and the side plate. A 3D view of the small scale model inside the test section is shown in Figure 2. The measurement inside the wind tunnel facility was planned to reach velocities up to 50 m/s, which corresponds to the Reynolds numbers based on the wing reference chord of up to 1.3×10^6 . However, lower inflow velocities, starting from 25 m/s, were considered as well. This was used to study different velocity ratios between the local external flow and the AFC actuator flow.

Figure 2: Small scale model inside the wind tunnel facility (Tel Aviv University).

The CFD simulations used the inflow velocity of 50 m/s, which was according to the large sale test. However, a separate study was done to evaluate the Reynolds number effect, considering inflow velocity of 25 m/s [5].

The instrumentation of the SSM consists of static pressure taps, which are installed along several lines, as shown in Figure 3. The chord-wise

Figure 3: Static pressure probes located in 2 chordwise and 2 spanwise rows.

pressure rows are perpendicular to the leading edge, in the same way as in the LSM. This is related to the fact that for the model an existing zero-sweep model was utilized for the design of LSM. The pressure rows were designed in exactly the same location to allow for direct comparison between the scaled models.

Pressure values were recorded using static pressure taps along two chordwise and two spanwise rows which are indicated by the solid and dashed lines in Figure 3, where also the number of pressure taps along each row is indicated. Several additional pressure sensors were located in the critical region, close to the leading edge, where the AFC actuators were placed.

2.1. AFC in the experiment

It is well known that the region which is susceptible to flow separation is the leading edge of the main wing, between the nacelle pylon and the inboard slat cut-out, see Figure 4, which shows area of negative streamwise skin friction velocity. In the previous project [4] the pulsed blowing as well as

Figure 4: Typical flow pattern: $AoA=15^\circ$, $V_\infty=50$ m/s, without actuation.

synthetic jets were considered for the AFC actuation. The addition of steady suction is a natural step forward.

The AFC actuator to be applied is the Suction and Oscillatory Blowing actuator [11]. The SaOB actuator consists of an ejector creating steady suction and a fluidic oscillator creating oscillatory blowing. Flow control capabilities of the SaOB actuator have already been demonstrated for drag reduction and separation postponement on the airfoils [10,11].

Figure 5 shows the internal structure of a generic SaOB actuator. Pressurized air is introduced into the actuator and accelerated in the ejector nozzle. The accelerated air creates an entraining effect, which can be used to suck boundary layer flow

from a nearby surface. The pressurized air and the sucked air mix in the ejector and enter the fluidic oscillator. Pressure equalization between the side walls of the fluidic oscillator can be realized by an feedback tube resulting into an alternating jet and eventually the oscillatory blowing is created. An adjustment of the feedback tube dimensions and the inlet pressure allows control of the oscillation frequency and the blowing magnitude. The properties of the SaOB actuator have been extensively studied [17], however, it has to be noted that several versions of SaOB actuator exist, not only in terms of scale, but also with different shape of blowing nozzle, which leads to, e.g., different shape of the outlet velocity profile.

Figure 5: Internal structure of the generic SaOB actuator.

The location of the actuators is limited by several factors. For instance it is limited by the size of the cavity available in the wind tunnel model, physical size of the actuators and the requirements for their placement given by suitable blowing direction. In our case, the chordwise location of the suction holes and the blowing slots was restricted by removable surface panel modules intended for actuator installation on the large scale model at TsAGI [14], which was kept also in the case of SSM for consistency of the results.

Several steps were taken to identify suitable position of the AFC actuators. They were partly based on the CFD results and will be discussed in the Section 3.

The final AFC setup includes four fluidic oscillators, each consisting of a set of blowing nozzles, and eight elliptical suction holes, see Figure 6.

The dimensions of the elliptical suction holes are 3mm x 2mm (major axis x minor axis). They are spaced equally along 1.5% of the local chord. The blowing nozzles outlet dimensions are 10 mm (spanwise) times 4 mm (chordwise). The blowing slots are located at 12.5% of the local chord and inclined approx. 30° toward the local model surface. The orientation on blowing slots is parallel to the leading edge rather than aligned with the streamwise direction. The whole array of actuators is connected and controlled by a synchronization tube [7]. This allows an in-phase operation of the fluidic oscillators array.

Figure 6: Placement of the suction holes (red) and blowing slots (blue). The area of actuation indicated by a red ellipse corresponds to Figure 4.

3. CFD SETUP

The CFD setup is closely related to the wind tunnel topology. The SSM and the main dimensions of the wind tunnel test sections are kept in order to obtain consistent installation effects, like wind tunnel blockage, interaction of the model with the boundary layer developed at the wind tunnel walls, etc. The CFD layout is seen in Figure 7.

The aim of the CFD activity is to obtain reliable results and validate them towards the wind tunnel measurements, provide support for the placement of the AFC devices and to predict AFC effect. Within the INAFLOWT project, three research groups focused on the CFD analysis. The diverse tools for the solutions of baseline flow as well as AFC actuated cases were employed, according to the individual experience and available solution methods.

Figure 7: Layout of the CFD model corresponding to the wind tunnel environment.

At VZLU, the CFD solver Edge, an unstructured finite volume flow solver for compressible flow [20], was used to run the simulations. Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equations were employed for simulations of both steady and time dependent problems. The steady-state RANS simulations were utilized for simulations of baseline flows and steady suction. The 2nd order spatial discretization with a Central scheme and time integration via semi-implicit dual time stepping approach is used. Various turbulence models were tested, however, for the present results the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence was used [13].

In terms of CFD mesh topology, traditional approach using conforming hybrid grids was generated with Pointwise software. The grid incorporated several structured blocks to capture vortical structures arising from the complicated geometry, such as strake, pylon, leading edge steps and slat edges. The cylindrical domain of the wing-pylon-nacelle model was rotated around the rotation axis to set the angle of attack (AoA) and conformingly connected to the rest of the domain, representing wind tunnel environment. With this approach, each case in terms of AoA or AFC actuator setup has to be generated independently. However, overall structure and topology of the grid in the vicinity of the SSM is maintained. The grid size for the case without flow control was nearly 40 million grid points, the flow control case with slightly increased the number of nodes to about 42 million. The increase is not significant due to the fact, that the blowing slots are represented by boundary conditions attached to the surfaces. The detail of the grid close to the AFC can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Detail of the grid in the AFC devices area. Suction holes (red) and blowing slots (green).

The boundary conditions were prescribed naturally according to the analogy with the wind tunnel environment. The SSM model surface was represented by adiabatic wall boundary conditions. The wind tunnel environment was prescribed the same boundary condition. Upper and lower wind tunnel wall was represented by a symmetry plane (Euler wall) boundary condition. Inlet and outlet to and from the wind tunnel section was represented by standard inflow and outflow boundary conditions. This applies to the baseline case.

The AFC devices were represented by a slight modification of the geometry and the appropriate boundary conditions. The steady suction, which was the first AFC mode, was partly modelled by suction holes, which were connected to the suction box underneath the wing surface. The outlet pressure boundary condition was prescribed at the bottom of the suction box. The blowing slots were represented by separate boundaries, which were modelled just below the original clean wing surface to avoid meshing problems arising from boundary layer grid topology. The variable, time-dependent velocity profile was prescribed according to the description given in [17]. Although the shape of the exit nozzle of the SaOB actuator used in this study is substantially different from the one used in the mentioned reference, the velocity profile variation with respect to the spanwise coordinate (along the local coordinate aligned with the span of the blowing slot) shows similar trends, namely that the peak velocity is observed close to the mid area between the pair of blowing slots, see Figure 9, in comparison to the measurements presented in Figure 12, where the mean velocity of slightly different SaOB configuration is shown.

Figure 9: Peak velocity profile of the SaOB actuator. Left (green) and right (red) blowing slot. Comparison of the hybrid RANS/LES simulation with the URANS (dashed lines) velocity profiles [17].

The parametric Gaussian representation of the velocity profile is used in the local coordinate system aligned with the blowing slot geometry, i.e., inclined by 30° towards the surface, etc. Since the normalized velocity profile is independent on the absolute velocity, the parametric description is easily adjustable for the required AFC parameters.

For the presented simulations, the peak blowing velocity was set to $U_{jet,max} = 150$ m/s, and the switching frequency to 300 Hz.

At the University of Stuttgart (USTUTT) the simulations were conducted using the unstructured finite volume flow solver DLR TAU code [16]. URANS equations were employed for simulations of time dependent actuation modes, while steady-state RANS simulations were utilized for simulations of steady actuation. Recent studies on a high-lift configuration [15] and a flat plate [6] demonstrate that in general a good agreement can be observed between measurements with AFC and RANS simulations by adjusting the numerical parameters.

The grid in the vicinity of the SSM wind tunnel model was identical to the one used by VZLU (baseline grid), but the connection to the wind tunnel environment grid was done with overlapping Chimera approach, see Figure 10

Also the AFC devices were represented by the Chimera blocks. This allows significant flexibility in terms of positioning of the AFC devices and is more suitable for parametric studies. The mesh in the vicinity of the actuator orifices was refined in comparison to the baseline background mesh to be able to resolve the actuator geometry and the flow phenomena resulting from interaction of AFC induced flow with the external boundary layer flow. The detail of the Chimera grid around the AFC actuators is shown in Figure 11

Figure 10: Chimera approach to set the AoA, overlapping grid differs in colours (USTUTT).

The SSM model and the wind tunnel environment are represented by standard boundary conditions described above. More precise description has to be dedicated to the boundary condition representing the AFC devices. Since the internal structure is simplified and largely avoided to save computational resources, the suction mechanism was modelled by an array of holes (tubes)

Figure 11: Detail of the AFC grid by Chimera approach (USTUTT).

Figure 12: Velocity profiles at the outlet of the blowing nozzles of the SaOB actuator [8].

connected to the common low pressure plenum and the pressure inside the cavity below the suction holes was applied at the bottom of the suction plenum for the simulations, corresponding to the measurements by a pressure sensor in the wind tunnel test.

The blowing slots were represented by simplified geometry, which represents an extrusion of the slot outlet geometry below the wing surface, taking into account the inclination angle of 30° toward the local wing surface. The prescribed velocity profiles were based on the spanwise measurement of the real outlet of the SaOB actuator. Velocity profiles at the outlets of the blowing nozzles were measured using a 3D traversing system with a single hotwire anemometer, see Figure 12. A switching quality, which represents the ratio between time-averaged velocity and its standard deviation, of approximately 0.7 was measured, which corresponds to a fully switched sine wave. The actuation boundary conditions implemented into the DLR TAU-Code comprise of harmonic or smoothed pulsed blowing BC [8].

For the simulations presented in the following the harmonic or sinusoidal blowing BC, with a maximum blowing velocity of $U_{jet,max} = 150$ m/s, was applied at the nozzle inlet, as it represents the switching mechanism of the investigated fluidic oscillator in the most accurate way. Therefore, the velocity ratio (VR) between the mean blowing jet velocity and the inflow velocity is $VR=1.5$. The actuation period is evenly distributed between the two blowing nozzles, which results in a duty cycle (DC) of 0.5. The actuation frequency of $f = 200$ Hz was selected

In total, four computational grids were employed for the present simulations: a baseline grid without AFC, a grid with suction holes only, a grid with blowing slots only and a grid with both suction holes and blowing slots. This allows for an independent assessment of the different actuation mechanisms.

IAI utilized a structured, patched grids or Chimera overset grid topology approach to model the SSM and the wind tunnel test section using CFD solver EZAir, developed by the Israeli CFD centre (ISCFDC) [18]. The 2nd order discretization of the k- ω -SST turbulence model [19] was used.

This approach also enables to rotate the SSM model along with its grids without re-meshing the entire model for different angles of attack in the wind tunnel environment.

Each individual part of the model was represented by a structured overlapping block, as we can see in Figure 13.

The grid was generated with Pointwise software. The total number of nodes was around 90 million. However, due to overlaps the subsequent pre-processing reduces the number of actively used nodes (live nodes) to approximately 85 million.

The use of AFC devices was also represented by additional Chimera blocks. The suction holes was represented by the suction tubes connected with the model surface, the blowing slots were represented by the refined block attached to the surface (surface boundary condition).

The pressure outlet boundary condition with prescribed static pressure represents the steady suction, while the oscillatory blowing was prescribed by uniform velocity profile, with the given 30° inclination towards the wing's surface. The harmonic function in time defines the oscillatory blowing. The adjacent slots are defined with opposite phase, see Figure 14.

4. RESULTS

Preparatory studies of the baseline flow [5] revealed that a sound agreement with wind tunnel test data, in terms of pressure distribution and flow separation characteristics, can be seen. For these results the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model in its original form (SAO) [13] has been used. For reasons of comparability of the actuation effects the simulations with AFC needs to be conducted with the same turbulence model and the same grid topology. Relative changes in the solutions given by application of the AFC can be small and the use of inconsistent data would smear the effects and contributions of each of the differences in the simulation.

A non-dimensional actuation frequency

$$F^+ = \frac{f \times c_{ref}}{U_\infty}, \quad (1)$$

which is used within this study is approximately 1.5 (for 200Hz actuation at 50 m/s freestream velocity) to 2.3 (for 300Hz actuation), based on the chord length of the clean wing c_{ref} . According to [12] the most effective non-dimensional frequency for separation control is on the order of unity. The frequencies are chosen according to typical performance of the SaOB actuators.

Another important characteristic parameter is the momentum coefficient

$$C_\mu = \frac{\dot{m} U_{jet}}{q_\infty S_{ref}}, \quad (2)$$

where \dot{m} denotes the time-averaged mass flow through the blowing nozzles and U_{jet} the time averaged jet velocity. The same principle and formula can be applied to the steady suction. The coefficient is scaled with the product of the dynamic pressure q_∞ and the model reference area S_{ref} . The combination of steady suction and steady or oscillatory blowing is more complicated, because the two AFC modes should be distinguished. Moreover, in the SaOB actuator, the sucked flow is added to the flow added by the external pressure source, so that the mass flow through the blowing nozzle is a sum of the two.

4.1. Optimal suction location

A parametrical study was performed by USTUT to identify optimal location of the row of suction holes. Three chordwise positions of spanwise row of suction holes (i.e. row of suction holes is arranged parallel to the wing leading edge) were evaluated. The suction-hole rows were placed at approximately 4.5% of the chord, 3% and 1.5% of the chord. Some limitations were necessary due to installation constrains for the LSM, where only certain removable panels can be used for this purposes. A number of 14 circular suction holes with a diameter of 2 mm and a spanwise distance of 8 mm were integrated into the inboard slat cut-out section of the wing, see Figure 11. The pressure prescribed at the bottom of the suction box (as described in Section 3) was set to -2.2 psi

Figure 13: Full Chimera grid, the blocks are distinguished by colour (top), overlaps visualized inside a streamwise cut (bottom).

Figure 14: Unsteady velocities defined in adjacent outlet slots, corresponding to a single SaOB actuator.

Figure 15: Slat cut-out area with surface streamlines and an area of negative c_{fx} contour at $AoA=15^\circ$ for baseline flow (left), and further to right: suction via 14 circular holes at $x/c=0.045$, at $x/c=0.015$, suction via 8 elliptic suction holes (larger cross sectional area) at $x/c=0.015$ and increased plenum pressure. (USTUTT).

(i.e., approximately 15kPa below atmospheric pressure). The simulations at $AoA=15^\circ$ reveal that the most upstream position of suction holes is the most beneficial from the point of view of reduction of the flow separation and also for the lift benefit, cf Table 1 and Figure 15. This trend was also confirmed by experiments [7].

The suction pressure was later reduced in order to comply with the realistic pressure of -1.5 psi which was available in the experimental setup. This led to a somewhat reduced efficiency of steady suction. However, the final setup of 8 elliptic suction holes with an increased spanwise spacing and similar total cross sectional area brought some recovery in the lift at much lower energy requirements.

Table 1: Lift benefit of steady suction with respect to the location of suction holes.

Actuation	Suction row location x/c	Suction pressure	dCL
Baseline	-	-	-
14 holes	4.5%	-2.2 psi	0.062
14 holes	3.0%	-2.2 psi	0.065
14 holes	1.5%	-2.2 psi	0.070
8 elliptic	1.5%	-1.5 psi	0.058

4.2. Validation and the results of the AFC cases

An in-depth comparison of the numerical simulations with measurement data at $U_\infty = 25$ m/s, including spanwise and chordwise pressure distributions, wake measurements and oil flow visualization, for the baseline flow can be found in [5], where also scaling and wind tunnel installation effects were studied, with respect to the wind tunnel models used within the project.

It is necessary to be said that the wind tunnel installation effect incorporates efficiency of the

LEX. In LSM this modification of the slat provides efficient mean how to prevent corner flow separation on the large scale. This is not completely true of the SSM, which is much more prone to boundary layer separation. The flow remains unstable and the cross comparison becomes more difficult. On the other hand, the area of interest is not necessarily influenced by these secondary flow features.

The inclusion of the AFC by means of steady suction or oscillatory blowing and validation against the wind tunnel experimental data is plotted in this section. The data generated by VZLU, as depicted in Figure 16, show typical picture, which is presented for the case of $AoA=13^\circ$. The comparison is given for baseline case and the

Figure 16: Outboard chordwise row, C_p comparison between experimental (squares) and CFD data (solid lines). $AoA=13^\circ$, the baseline case (black) and the steady suction (red) is depicted (VZLU).

steady suction. We can see that the effect of actuation is limited, with the exception of the flap data. It has to be noted, however, that the position

of the pressure taps row does not cross directly the area that is the most influenced by the AFC actuation, which is the region downstream of the inboard slat cut-out area. Therefore, significant effect is observed in the 2nd spanwise row, and primarily in its inboard area, cf. Figure 17, indicated by green ellipse. Although there are visible differences in the total values of the C_p , the increased suction has similar magnitude. Let us note that the range of the vertical axis is smaller in comparison to Figure 16.

This Figure show only baseline case compared to

Figure 17: Front and rear spanwise row in the same notation and conditions as Figure 16. The green ellipse shows the area of inboard part of the rear spanwise cut. Baseline (black) is compared to steady suction (red) for experimental data (squares) and CFD (solid lines).

the steady suction. Similar plots by USTUTT show similar trends also for wider range of AoA, cf. Figure 18 for AoA=10° and 15°. The small inconsistency, which can be observed in the leading edge area of the outboard cut, can be attributed to small differences in the geometry between the CFD model and the experimental setup (a gap between slat end and the wing). More detailed evolution of the spanwise distribution of C_p is visible in Figure 19, where the difference between baseline and the steady suction is qualitatively indicated, cf. Figure 17,

Figure 19: Evolution of C_p on several spanwise cuts. Baseline is indicated by black lines (blue on flap) and steady suction red/magenta on flap. Indication of chordwise pressure tap sections (dashed black). The area influenced by AFC shown in green ellipse (VZLU).

where the quantitative results are presented. The baseline is plotted in black line and the actuated case by red lines. For visibility, flap is shown in blue (baseline) and magenta (steady suction). This figure demonstrates the extent of the typical C_p

Figure 18: Pressure distributions for baseline and AFC flow (steady suction, SaOB effect) for a range of AoA. Inboard chordwise pressure row (top) and outboard row (bottom) is shown (USTUTT).

benefit given by the actuation and its relation to the available instrumentation of the wind tunnel model (pressure taps rows). The area downstream of the AFC panel is influenced, as indicated by the green ellipse. A slight rearrangement of the flow is, however, visible also on the outboard part. IAI presents the C_p data of streamwise cut crossing the area of AFC actuators. Clear distinction between baseline and the actuated cases is seen in Figure 20. Here, all the presented modes of AFC renew the pressure peak lost due to the flow separation.

Figure 20: Comparison of streamwise cut crossing the area of AFC actuators at $AoA=12^\circ$ (IAI).

Area of the negative streamwise skin friction extends from the leading edge region between inboard slat cut-out and the pylon axis. This area, depicted blue in, e.g., Figure 15 ($AoA=15^\circ$) or Figure 21 ($AoA=17^\circ$), has one root in directly at the pylon axis, which is caused by a strong vortex emanating from the pylon junction. The second place of origin is the leading edge area closer to the inboard slat step, caused by leading edge flow separation.

The steady suction is able to reduce the negative streamwise skin friction area. However, the pylon

induced negative skin friction persists, even at lower AoA .

For high AoA , the separated area extends from to the trailing edge of the wing. Steady suction reduces the separation area, but it is still extended downstream of the suction holes. The oscillatory blowing provides the energy and re-aligns the flow in the streamwise direction, cancelling the negative surface streamlines, see Figure 21.

5. CONCLUSION

The application of AFC defined by steady suction and oscillatory blowing was investigated on a small scale generic UHBR high lift configuration. The approach of three different research groups was described and the available results were presented.

Four cases were commented, namely the baseline configuration, the individual effect of the flow control mechanisms given by steady suction, oscillatory blowing and a combination of both.. Validation of CFD with wind tunnel test data shows an adequate agreement in both, the baseline flow and the similar trends are seen also in the actuated flows.

Individual actuation mechanisms demonstrate promising results in the reduction of separation caused by the extended slat cutout and the UHBR engine nacelle integration.

The AFC in the slat cutout region does not only reduce the area of flow separation, but also affects the complex highly 3D vortical flow field. The interaction effects between AFC and the vortices show that the problem is highly complex and that various dependencies make the assessment of AFC difficult. It was found that due to the reattachment of the flow and the reorientation of the vortices in the slat cutout region the effect of AFC is extended to the region downstream of the installation area of the actuators.

The results presented here, however, contribute to the final goal, which is the study of AFC effects on near full scale, which will be studied again both numerically and experimentally during the future course of the project

Figure 21: Slat cutout area with surface streamlines and contour of negative streamwise skin friction at $AoA=17^\circ$ for baseline and actuated flow by indicated AFC methods (USTUTT).

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7. REFERENCES

- Reducing emissions from aviation. https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/aviation_en [retrieved 13-January-2020].
- Rudnik, R.: Stall behaviour of the EUROLIFT high lift configurations. In: *46th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*. Reno, Nevada (2008). p. 836.
- Cordis, INAFLOWT https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210820_en.html [retrieved 13-January-2020].
- Cordis, AFLoNext <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/109010/reporting/en> [retrieved 13-January-2020].
- Ullah, J., Prachař, A., Šmíd, M., Seifert, A., Soudakov, V., Lutz, T. and Kramer, E.: Reynolds Number and Wind Tunnel Effects on the Flow Field Around a Generic UHBR Engine High-Lift Configuration, In *Proceedings of the 54th 3AF International Conference on Applied Aerodynamics*, Paris, 2019.
- Ullah, J., Shay, N., Possti, M., Seifert, A., Lutz, T., Kramer, E.: Capability of RANS Simulations to Reproduce Flat Plate Boundary Layer Interaction with Suction and Oscillatory Blowing, *Notes on Numerical Fluid Mechanics and Multidisciplinary Design*, Volume 142, Springer, Germany, 2019. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-25253-3
- Possti M., Ariel Y., Ullah J., Seifert A.: Active control of wing-engine-slat cutout region flow separation, In *Proceedings of the 54th 3AF International Conference on Applied Aerodynamics*, Paris, 2019.
- Ullah, J., Shay, N., Seifert, A., Lutz, T., Kramer, E.: Active Flow Separation Control on a Generic UHBR Engine High-Lift onfiguration by Means of Suction and Oscillatory Blowing, *SFB 880 Final Symposium*, Braunschweig, December 2019.
- Arwatz, G., Fono, I., Seifert, A.: Suction and Oscillatory Blowing Actuator. In: Morrison J.F. Birch D.M., Lavoie P. (eds) *IUTAM Symposium on Flow Control and MEMS*. IUTAM Bookseries, vol 7. Springer, Dordrecht (2008).
- Schatzman, D., Wilson, J., Arad, E., Seifert, A., Shtendel, T.: Drag-Reduction Mechanisms of Suction-and-Oscillatory-Blowing Flow Control, *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 52, No. 11 (2014), pp. 2491-2505. doi:10.2514/1.J052903
- Seifert, A., Bachar, T., Koss, D., Shepshelovits, M. Wygnanski, I.: "Oscillatory Blowing, a Tool to Delay Boundary Layer Separation", *AIAA J.* Vol. 31, No. 11 (1993), pp. 2052-2060. doi:10.2514/6.1993-440.
- Seifert, A., Darabi, A., Wygnanski, I.: Delay of Airfoil Stall by Periodic Excitation, *AIAA J.* Vol. 33, No. 4 (1996), pp. 691-698. doi:10.2514/3.47003.
- Spalart, P. R., Allmaras, S. R.: A One-Equation Turbulence Model for Aerodynamic Flows. In *30th Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*, page 439, 1992.
- Soudakov, V., Amiryants, G., Schlosser, P., Bauer, M., Weigel, P., Bardet, M., Ciobaca, V., Gebhardt, A., Wild, J.: Full-Scale Wind-Tunnel Test of Active Flow Control at the Wing/Pylon/Engine Junction. Presentation held at CEAS 2017, Bucharest, Romania.
- Ciobaca, V.: Validation of numerical simulations for separation control on high lift configurations. Dissertation, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt eV, Bibliotheks- und Informationswesen, 2014.
- Schwaborn, D., Gerhold, T., Heinrich, R.: The DIR Tau-Code, Recent Applications in Research and Industry. In: *European Conference on Computational Fluid Dynamics ECCOMAS CFD (2006)*
- Vrchota, P., Prachař, A., Hospodář, P.: Verification of Boundary Conditions Applied to Active Flow Circulation Control, *Aerospace* 2019, 6, 34; DOI 10.3390/aerospace6030034
- ISCFDC website : <https://iscfdc.co.il/> [retrieved 30 January 2020]
- TMR website : <https://turbmodels.larc.nasa.gov/sst.html> [retrieved 30 January 2020]
- Eliasson, P., "EDGE, a Navier-Stokes Solver for Unstructured Grids", *Proceedings to Finite Volume for Complex Applications III.*, ISTE Ltd., London, 2002, pp. 527-534